

Carbon-Based Hybrid Supercapacitors for High Power Photovoltaic Irrigation

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Abstract

A photovoltaic pumping system comprises the following components: a solar photovoltaic (PV) installation, a variable frequency converter, a motor-pump, and a water source. The application combines solar PV technology, hydraulic engineering, and high-efficiency water management techniques to optimize irrigated farming. In the last decades, a growing trend has been observed in the application of renewable energies, which depend on the weather and daily conditions. In the case of cloud passing periods, the generation of energy by the photovoltaic system is drastically reduced, which will affect the overall general operation of the system. To better account for the considered operating parameters of a high-power PV pumping system, dedicated control algorithms have been developed in recent years [1], with the aim of mitigating solar power intermittency. One of the options that can be considered to avoid the sudden change in power generated by the solar PV system is to integrate an energy storage system that could accommodate those changes. In this way, carbon-based hybrid supercapacitors (HSupercap) represent the opportunity to solve this issue with a cost effective and long-lasting energy storage system, controlling PV power ramp rate, improving its overall lifetime. The HSupercap was installed, configured and tested in order to characterize it and assess this possibility of integration. The tested system presented overall performance characteristics suitable for its application in high power photovoltaic pumping or irrigation.

Presentation of the system installed at the experimental grid

Main Characteristics of the HSupercap module tested [2]

- ❖ Nominal Capacity (@1C): 45 Ah (±5%)
- ❖ Nominal Energy: 2,61 kWh
- ❖ Nominal Voltage: 55,0 V
- ❖ No thermal run-away
- ❖ Power Density: 1500 W/kg
- ❖ Dimensions (cm): 50,0 × 35,0 × 18,0
- ❖ Weight of Powerpack: 57,36 kg
- ❖ Cycles Life @ 25°C: >20 000

Figure 1: a) Side View of two modules of the HSupercap; b) Top View of the HSupercap

HSupercap Operating Mode

- ❖ Through programming developed in LabVIEW [3] and using Modbus TCP-IP communication protocol, the HSupercap can charge or discharge according to the command given by the control unit;
- ❖ Commands can be sent to charge or discharge a given power setpoint to the Hsupercap.
- ❖ The simplified schematic below presents a possible integration setup for a high-power PV irrigation system. Different setups are possible (off-grid or on-grid) and /or hybridized with other power sources (such as a diesel gen-set).

Figure 2: Example of integration of a HSupercap in a high-power photovoltaic system

Results

Efficiency values obtained – inverters and HSupercap

The charge and discharge average efficiency values of the inverters (experimental setup with 3 inverters – one per phase) obtained at different power levels were in all cases above 82%. Average efficiency values above 100% were calculated, nevertheless within the calculated error interval. The roundtrip average energy efficiency of the HSupercap was 97.8% (±3.6%).

DC Voltage curve in a Charging State

Tests were performed up to 8C charging rate (as well as discharge), as the inverters installed were not able to operate at higher currents. At 2C a charge duration of 830s was obtained. These tests were performed for a voltage range of 45V – 56V (manufacturer specs: discharge cut-off voltage 39.6V; max. charge voltage 57.2V).

Cloud passing PV power ramp rate control

This hybrid powercapacitor module provides a response time of <200ms (for a 3600A pulse discharge), and a max. sustained power capability of 29.7 kW. In standby mode, the system is able to achieve a response time <2s (for a low latency network). Given a typical cloud passing as shown below, with 20s duration, this system proves to have a response time suitable to control the PV power ramp rate.

Conclusions

- ❖ The inverters presented high average efficiency values, for charge and discharge modes.
- ❖ The HSupercap tested presented an average roundtrip energy efficiency of 97.8%.
- ❖ The tested system was not able to achieve higher power than 20 kW due to current limits of the inverters. Proper sizing of the inverters and cabling proves to be key to unlock the HSupercap full power capabilities.
- ❖ Additional optimization work should be carried in order to achieve lower control runtime, reaching an overall <1s response time.
- ❖ Additional tests will be carried out, integrating this HSupercap with a real size PV pumping test rig, in order to reach a full experimental validation for this application type.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the support of this work, partly funded by European Union's H2020 programme as part of the SolaQua project (Accessible, reliable, and affordable solar irrigation for Europe and beyond), Grant agreement ID 952789.

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